

STRAIN RATE DEPENDENT FAILURE OF METALLIC INTERFACES AT NANO-MICROSCALE VIA NANOIMPACT EXPERIMENTS

Devendra Verma¹ and Vikas Tomar¹

¹School of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Purdue University, West Lafayette, IN 47907, USA.
Corresponding Author, Email: tomar@purdue.edu, Tel: 765-494-3423

Keywords: Interface Strength, High Strain Rate, Dynamic Loading, Electron Microscopy, Rate Dependent Constitutive Models

ABSTRACT

Ti/Steel interfaces are produced using Field Assisted Sintering Technology (FAST), a technique known to bring about full consolidation of materials using much lower sintering temperatures and durations. The interface thickness is verified using the Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis exhibiting extent of diffusion in interface regions. The interface mechanical strength is characterized using dynamic indentation experiments at strain rates approaching 400 s^{-1} . The experiments were conducted on the interfaces within the spatial error tolerance of less than $3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ s. The measurements of dynamic hardness, strain rates, and plastic-residual depths were correlated to show the relation of interface mechanical strength with the bulk phase mechanical strength properties of Ti and steel. The JC model is fitted to the obtained interface normal stress- normal strain data based on the nano-impact experiments. Results show that interfacial properties are affected by the rate of loading and also are largely dependent upon the interface structural inhomogeneity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic materials damage occurs under a variety of loading conditions such as sand particle erosion, shot peening, and projectile impact etc. While a significant research effort has focused upon developing polycrystalline material constitutive laws under impact, the dynamic interface constitutive behavior remains largely uninvestigated [1]. Recent progress in dynamic loading failure investigations have shown that interfaces play a significant part in determining material failure [1]. The present work focuses on investigating interface failure under dynamic impact loading. Several material constitutive models have been developed to show the effect of strain rate on the dynamic strength of materials [2-5]. During the impact loading events, stress waves or shock waves propagate inside the impacted bodies and large inelastic deformations develop. Because of the complexity of the deformations at higher strain rates, the development of material models needs intelligently designed experiments. Split Hopkinson bar experiment is a popular method to conduct high strain rate experiments in the tensile and compression mode to model the dynamic material behavior [6]. The experimental procedure involves impact on bulk material. On the other hand, the development of nanoindentation techniques in the last decades has allowed us to model the site specific behavior such as at the interface between two materials at higher strain rates [7]. The present work focuses on using such technique.

The interface between aerospace alloys: Ti-6AL-4V alloy (Ti64) and 304 stainless steel (SS) [8-20] has been investigated thoroughly in material science due to their prevalent applications in aerospace and automotive industries. The most common practice is to produce such interface using direct solid state diffusion bonding. However, direct diffusion bonding of Ti64/SS leads to problems such as intermetallic brittle phase formation and residuals stress at the interfaces. As a result, bond strength of such interfaces drops due to the increase in the interface thickness. The diffusion of Ti, Al and V mainly relies on vacancies, dislocations and grain boundaries during hot pressing [20]. In the case of diffusion bonding of dissimilar materials, an interlayer inserted between substrates is often necessary to prevent the formation of intermetallic compound and to reduce the residual stress in the

joints. Interlayer used in titanium alloy and stainless steel joints has several advantages such as: low residual stress in the indirect bonded joint because the interlayer material serves as a buffer for low pressure required within the bonding zone during a joining process.

In order to understand the underlying mechanisms and structure of interfaces along with their mechanical strength, characterization techniques with sufficient resolution are needed. However, until recently, the investigation of material deformation with electron microscopy has been limited to bulk phase properties. In this work, the interface properties at Ti/Steel interfaces are probed by nanoscale impact experiments. The novelty of the experiments lies in the fact that impacts are precisely at the interfaces in the precision range of nanometers to micrometers as required by the material microstructure. The probe used for impact has tip radius of 40 nm. This tip impacts at the interfaces thus making sure that energy from the impact is delivered at the interfacial region. The impact stress-strain data from experiments is fitted to Johnson-Cook (JC) constitutive model to define the material behavior at high strain rates.

2. METHODS

2.1. MATERIAL

Ti-6Al-4V/304 stainless steel interfaces were prepared by compressing Ti64 and stainless steel together at 45 MPa at 975 °C for 10 minutes. Sintering experiments were carried out in a FCT's FAST 250 ton system. The Ti/Steel interface was processed using Field Assisted Sintering Technology (FAST), a technique known to bring about full consolidation of materials using much lower sintering temperatures and durations. The sintering was carried out by concurrently applying temperature pressure and high current density. The maximum load capability of FAST is 250 ton with maximum displacement of 300 mm. The allowable temperature ranges are from room temperature up to 2400 °C. The SEM image of the final sample is shown in Figure 1. The tip of the indenter in the dynamic indentations was 30 nm. It enables to perform indents exactly at the interface. The indentation set up is equipped with a microscope that is used to examine the indentation area before experiments, and to choose specific sites to perform impacts.

Figure 1 SEM image showing Ti/Steel interface

2.2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE: DYNAMIC INDENTATION

The dynamic indentations were performed using the high strain rate impact schedule of Micro Materials, UK [21-24]. The experimental set up consists of the 3D stage to mount the sample that allows it to move in all x, y and z directions. The indents were performed with a cube corner indenter.

The indenter is mounted on a pendulum that is hanging vertically on frictionless springs to let it move freely. The force on the pendulum is applied through the electromagnets as shown in Figure 2. The depth of the indent is measured as function of change in the capacitance of the plates attached at the back of the indenter. It allows for high accuracy of measurements in depth measurements. The additional force for high strain rate impacts is provided with the help of a solenoid situated at the lower part of the pendulum. Load and depth calibrations were performed before the experiments and the instrument was kept inside a thermally stable chamber on a vibration isolation table. During the impacts, the force is applied with both electromagnets and the solenoid to the pendulum, which means it is being pulled at both ends. At the instant of impact, the solenoid is turned off which releases the pendulum and it hits the sample. The load of the dynamic indentation is predefined in the experiment. The initial impact and the subsequent rebound depth versus time history is also recorded. This data is further analyzed to calculate the dynamic hardness, maximum strain, strain rate, impact depth, stress at maximum depth, stress rate, impact velocity at the time of impact and in rebound stage, coefficient of restitution and energy absorbed during indentation.

Figure 2 Schematic of instrument set up for dynamic indentation tests

From its initial stationary solenoid position, the indenter position is monitored continuously as a function of time t , including the initial impact trajectory and the initial rebound from the material surface [7]. During single impact experiments, a typical depth versus time history is shown in Figure 3. The velocity of the indenter can be calculated as the first derivative of the response marked with V_{in} Figure 3. The maximum depth, the initial contact velocity, the outgoing velocity, the residual depth are calculated from this data. The residual depth is the position at the point of detachment from the sample on the first rebound. The strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$, of the impact changes with the depth of impact. An average strain rate characterizing the impact can be approximated by the expression

$$\dot{\epsilon} \approx \frac{V_{in}}{h_{max}}. \quad (1)$$

Where, h_{\max} is the maximum depth and V_{in} is the maximum velocity. The kinetic energy consumed in the plastic work done by indenter is given as [25, 26]

$$\frac{m(V_{in}^2 - V_{out}^2)}{2} = \int_0^{h_{res}} P dh . \quad (2)$$

Where, m is the mass of pendulum, P is the indentation load, V_{out} is the outgoing velocity of indenter and h_{res} is the residual depth of the impact. The projected area for the cube corner indenter is, $A_c = ch^2$ with $c = 2.59$. The effective dynamic hardness, H_d is then defined as derived by H. Somekawa and C.A. Schuh [26],

$$H_d = \frac{3m(V_{in}^2 - V_{out}^2)}{2ch_{res}^3} . \quad (3)$$

Figure 3 Data output from high strain rate impact tests, depth data marked with h_{\max} and velocity data marked with V_{in}

The strain rate in the dynamic indentations was in the range of 10 to 400 s^{-1} . These strain rates in the current experiment depends on the maximum load applied at the impacts. The highest load was applied to observe the behavior of material under highest deformation state. The impacts were conducted at the interface of the two metals and the in the bulk phase of both materials

2.3. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (SEM) AND ENERGY DISPERSIVE X-RAY (EDX)

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images were obtained by FEI Nova nanoSEM. The working distance for Nova SEM was 5 mm with 5.00 kV accelerating voltage in high vacuum chamber. Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was performed using FEI Quanta 3D FEG Dual-beam SEM. The working distance for Quanta SEM was 10 mm with 20.00 kV accelerating voltage in high vacuum chamber and cryogenic environment.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. EDX ANALYSIS OF DIFFUSION BONDED JOINTS

The EDX analysis was conducted to verify the site post-impact. Figure 4 shows SEM image of the impact marks on the surface of the sample. The width of the indent marks is in the range of 1-5 microns. The depth of the indents were in the range of 1-4 microns. The sites of the indents at the interface were confirmed by the elemental mapping of the surface as shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 (a) shows the impact area in the interfaces region, which is further verified in the elemental spectrum shown in Figure 5 (b). Figure 6 illuminates the diffused region where Fe and Ti phases are diffused into each other. The individual element mapping of Ti and Fe are shown in Figure 6 (a) and Figure 6 (b), respectively. Stainless steel has close packed *fcc* structure, hence, the extent of diffusion of Ti elements across the bond line is limited as evident from Figure 6 (a) with Ti elements mostly in the left region of the image. On the contrary, owing to more open crystallography of *bcc* matrix, Fe atoms can penetrate further in to the titanium lattice as shown in Figure 6 (b) with Fe elements also present in the left region of the image. The samples were prepared at a temperature of 975 °C, which is closer to the beta phase transition temperature [27] of Ti64 and the diffusion of the chemical species becomes easier through the interlayer, i.e. Ti can migrate to Fe side and vice versa.

Figure 4 Post impact SEM image of Ti/Steel surface

Figure 5 (a) EDX image with indent mark and (b) Elemental spectrum

Figure 6 EDX elemental map of (a) Ti and (b) Fe (Steel)

3.2. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF DIFFUSION BONDED JOINTS

The dynamic indentation data is analyzed to calculate the dynamic hardness of the specimen interfaces, strain rate during impact, depth during impact, stress at maximum depth, velocity of impact and energy absorbed during impact. These measurements are highly variable, and their uncertainty increases with dynamic or strain rate effects [28]. Here, the uncertainty is the change in the measurement of one parameter with respect to change in the other parameter. The variability in the experimental dynamic indentation data results from uncertainties associated with the testing conditions and loading apparatus. The measured values of dynamic hardness, strain impact, impact depth, etc. reflect this uncertainty in the loading and measurement, and the fundamental composition and behavior of the interface material. Figure 8 shows the influence of strain rate on the resulting uncertainty in impact depth. The measured properties are therefore presented as a function of strain rates in the analysis given in the following sections.

Figure 7 Influence of strain rate on the measured maximum impact depth

A check was performed on the data for the statistical analysis. The data for the dynamic indentation was analyzed using statistical analysis software SAS. A program was written in SAS to check the correlation between the dynamic hardness and the parameters of the experiment.

Table I shows the correlation coefficients of the dynamic hardness corresponding to the strain rate, plastic depth defined by maximum depth of impact, residual depth, stress rate and energy absorbed during impact. The stress rate was calculated as change in the stress from the initial point of contact to the maximum depth. The stress was calculated at the maximum depth and multiplied by the strain rate to find the stress rate. Dynamic hardness shows a strong positive correlations (>90) with strain rate and stress rate for the Ti and Fe phase but shows relatively weaker correlation for the interface region. Similarly high positive correlations are shown for the stress rates but lower correlations at the interface region. The depth of impact shows the similar negative correlations for residual depths but lower negative correlation for the plastic depth in the case of interface region. In all cases the absorbed energy during the impacts shows correlations in the similar range. These correlations are evidence to the fact that constitutive behavior of material in interface regions is different that of the bulk material phases.

H _{dyn}	Strain rate	h _{plastic}	h _{res}	Stress rate	E _{absorbed}
Ti/Steel	0.73931	-0.47867	-0.77260	0.50780	0.67832
Ti	0.93366	-0.80457	-0.76827	0.92681	0.53431
Steel	0.90321	-0.70209	-0.83883	0.87092	0.65154

Table I Correlation coefficients for the Dynamic Hardness with respect to Strain rate, Plastic depth of impact, Residual depth of impact, Stress rate and Energy Absorbed at impact at interface region, Ti and Steel.

The dynamic hardness has a positive correlation to the strain rate and stress rate while a negative correlation with the plastic and residual depth of the. Figure 8 shows that in the case of Ti/Steel samples, the hardness of the interface region starts at higher position than steel at lower strain rates but with the increase in the strain rate, it is less than the bulk material.

Figure 8 Trend of dynamic hardness on Ti/Steel interfaces with (a) strain rate (b) stress rate

The interface hardness is closer to the hardness of steel as seen from the 95% confidence interval bounds in Figure 8 showing a deviation from the trends of bulk phases at higher strain rates. It shows the same trend for the hardness of these samples from quasi-static experiments as shown in Figure 9 where the hardness of the interface regions falls within the same range as steel. As shown, the quasi-static hardness value based on standard Vicker's test is significantly higher than the dynamic hardness values. The length scale of measurement in Vickers test is a few 100 μm . The length scale in the case of the nano-impact experiments is 1-5 μm . This shows that the current nano-impact test is better

suites to evaluate the hardness of the material at the nano and micro scale microstructure such as at the interfaces.

Figure 9 Trend of Vickers Hardness in low strain rate experiments on Ti/Steel interfaces

3.3. JOHNSON-COOK CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

There are different dynamic strength models available in the literature that are applicable to varying strain rate range and loading conditions. One example is Steinberg-Guinan (SG) [2] model for the one-dimensional dynamic deformation response of isotropic materials subjected to longitudinal plate impact experiments. SG model cannot be used to characterize the instantaneous state of the material nor capture its evolving history. This model is useful for modeling many aspects of plate impact experiments at high rates including melting, strain hardening, and elastic-plastic wave interactions. The JC [3] dynamic strength model is one of the most popular one that gives an empirical description of the flow stress dependence on effective plastic strain, strain rate, and temperature. The JC model is the product of empirical relations used to describe strain hardening, strain rate hardening, and thermal softening up to strain rates of 10^4 s^{-1} . Steinberg and Lund (SL) [5] proposed a model to address limitations of the SG model, such as the inability to capture strain-rate dependent material behavior that directly incorporates a rate-dependent strength and can be used to model strain rates as low as 10^{-4} s^{-1} . Similarly, Zerilli and Armstrong (ZA) [4] proposed a constitutive model based on a partitioning the total strength into contributions from an athermal part, a thermal part, and a grain size dependent part. It can model the behavior of material for strain rates higher than 10^4 s^{-1} . The Mechanical Threshold Stress (MTS) [29] model is based on using a single internal state variable (ISV) to describe the evolving structure of the material. This model fits within the context of internal state variable theory of viscoplastic deformation for strain rate up to 10^4 s^{-1} but it is more complex to apply. For the high strain rates encountered in shock loading $\geq 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, the SG and SL model are the simplest models to implement. In the current case, however with strain rates lower than 10^4 s^{-1} , JC model is the most applicable model due to the least number of material parameters used in the model. The JC constitutive model [3] is an empirical model, where equivalent stress is given as a function of the strain, and strain rate and temperature as follows

$$\sigma = [A + B \varepsilon^n][1 + C \ln \dot{\varepsilon}][1 - T^{*m}]. \quad (4)$$

Here, σ is the equivalent stress, ε is the effective plastic strain and $\dot{\varepsilon}$ is the normalized effective plastic strain rate (normalized to strain rate of 1.0 s^{-1} in the present case). T^* is defined as $T^* = (T - T_r) / (T_m - T_r)$ with T_r as room temperature, T_m is the melting temperature and T is the absolute temperature. A , B , n , C and m are material constants. In the present case, the temperature during the experiments is the room temperature so the Equation (4) simplifies to

$$\sigma = [A + B \varepsilon^n][1 + C \ln \dot{\varepsilon}]. \quad (5)$$

The stress-strain data from the dynamic indentation experiments was fitted with the JC model to find the material constants. During the dynamic indentation experiments, the stress data for the strain from 0.2 to 0.4 is measured. The strain in the indentation with spherical indenters is defined in the literature as the contact radius divided by the radius of the indenter with a constant to take into account the experimental conditions [30, 31]. Cube corner indenter is used in the current experiment, so to take into account the three dimensional effects, the strain is defined as the residual area divided by the maximum area of contact during the impacts. The JC model Equation (5) is fitted on this range of strain considering an average strain rate of 300 s^{-1} during the experiments. The calculated material parameters are given in

Table II. The fitted curves from the Johnson Cook model are given in Figure 10.

Table II shows that the yield stress parameter (A) for the interface is lower than the Ti and steel. But the value of parameter ' B ' and n are higher as compared to the steel phase. This behavior is particular interest in the interfacial region showing that although it starts to yield at yield stresses comparable to steel, it has higher strain hardening rate. The deformation mechanisms of materials at high strain regime depends on the microstructure, strain rates, dislocation movements, and grain boundaries/orientations [32]. The present analysis shows dynamic indentation as a tool to capture the material deformation behavior with high precision at micrometer scales. These material parameters can be further used to describe the material behavior at the interface and in the homogeneous phases up to strain rates of 10^4 s^{-1} . All parameters are derived from the dynamic indentation experiments with high precision in the measurements and the locations of indentation as shown in *Figure 4* and *Figure 7*. The temperature effect is neglected in the present analysis because all experiment are conducted at room temperature.

	A (MPa)	B (MPa)	C	n
Ti/Steel Interface	111	3400	0.0010	0.54
Ti	676	5750	0.0012	0.61
Steel	156	1950	0.0011	0.20

Table II Materials Parameters from Johnson Cook Model

Figure 10 Stress-Strain response for (a) Ti, (b) Ti/Steel Interface and (c) Steel in dynamic indentation test at strain rate of 300 s^{-1}

4. CONCLUSION

Dynamic indentation based small scale impact experiments were performed on solid diffusion bonded Ti/Steel. The EDX analysis was performed post indentation to verify the impact sites and elemental maps of the sites were obtained to show the diffusion region at the interfaces. The conclusions of the dynamic tests are as follows:

1. The dynamic hardness as a function of strain rate and stress rate shows different trends of the interface strength in comparison to the bulk phases.
2. The correlation coefficients between dynamic, strain rate, stress rate, plastic depth, residual depth and absorbed energy during impacts shows that bulks phase have the similar correlations but the interface regions has varying trends.
3. The JC model is fitted to the stress-strain data to find the material parameters to define the deformation behavior of the material with an account of inhomogeneity in the structure at the interface and nearby regions at high strain rates.

These results shows the need to better address the constitutive behavior of the interfacial regions and nano-impact tests used in the current paper serves as one excellent tool to characterize the interfaces.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their sincere thanks to the excellent technical assistance of Dr. Christopher J. Gilpin, Chia-Ping Huang and Laurie Mueller with the Scanning Electron Microscopy at Purdue University. I would also like to thank my colleagues Dr. Ming Gan, Dr. You Sung Han, Dr. Hongsuk Lee, Tao Qu, Yang Zhang and Sudipta Biswas for helpful discussions. This research is supported by NSF grant CMMI1121113.

REFERENCES

- [1] B.D. Beake, S.R. Goodes, J.F. Smith and F. Gao: Nanoscale repetitive impact testing of polymer films, *Journal of materials research*. **19**(01), 237 (2004).
- [2] D. Steinberg, S. Cochran and M. Guinan: A constitutive model for metals applicable at high-strain rate, *Journal of Applied Physics*. **51**(3), 1498 (1980).
- [3] G.R. Johnson and W.H. Cook: A constitutive model and data for metals subjected to large strains, high strain rates and high temperatures, in *Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on Ballistics*, (**21**, The Netherlands, City, 1983), pp. 541.
- [4] F.J. Zerilli and R.W. Armstrong: Dislocation-mechanics-based constitutive relations for material dynamics calculations, *Journal of Applied Physics*. **61**(5), 1816 (1987).
- [5] D. Steinberg and C. Lund: A constitutive model for strain rates from 10^{-4} to 10^6 s⁻¹, *Journal of Applied Physics*. **65**(4), 1528 (1989).
- [6] W.-S. Lee and C.-F. Lin: Plastic deformation and fracture behaviour of Ti–6Al–4V alloy loaded with high strain rate under various temperatures, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. **241**(1), 48 (1998).
- [7] G. Constantinides, C. Tweedie, N. Savva, J. Smith and K. Van Vliet: Quantitative impact testing of energy dissipation at surfaces, *Experimental mechanics*. **49**(4), 511 (2009).
- [8] S. Kundu, M. Ghosh, A. Laik, K. Bhanumurthy, G. Kale and S. Chatterjee: Diffusion bonding of commercially pure titanium to 304 stainless steel using copper interlayer, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. **407**(1), 154 (2005).
- [9] S. Kundu, M. Ghosh and S. Chatterjee: Diffusion bonding of commercially pure titanium and 17-4 precipitation hardening stainless steel, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. **428**(1), 18 (2006).

- [10] S. Kundu and S. Chatterjee: Characterization of diffusion bonded joint between titanium and 304 stainless steel using a Ni interlayer, *Materials Characterization*. **59**(5), 631 (2008).
- [11] A. Elrefaey and W. Tillmann: Solid state diffusion bonding of titanium to steel using a copper base alloy as interlayer, *Journal of materials processing technology*. **209**(5), 2746 (2009).
- [12] S. Kundu, S. Sam and S. Chatterjee: Interface microstructure and strength properties of Ti–6Al–4V and microduplex stainless steel diffusion bonded joints, *Materials & Design*. **32**(5), 2997 (2011).
- [13] S. Kundu, S. Sam and S. Chatterjee: Evaluation of interface microstructure and mechanical properties of the diffusion bonded joints of Ti–6Al–4V alloy to microduplex stainless steel, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. **528**(15), 4910 (2011).
- [14] S. Kundu, D. Roy, S. Chatterjee, D. Olson and B. Mishra: Influence of interface microstructure on the mechanical properties of titanium/17-4 PH stainless steel solid state diffusion bonded joints, *Materials & Design*. **37**, 560 (2012).
- [15] P. Li, J. Li, J. Xiong, F. Zhang and S.H. Raza: Diffusion bonding titanium to stainless steel using Nb/Cu/Ni multi-interlayer, *Materials Characterization*. **68**, 82 (2012).
- [16] S. Sam, S. Kundu and S. Chatterjee: Diffusion bonding of titanium alloy to microduplex stainless steel using a nickel alloy interlayer: Interface microstructure and strength properties, *Materials & Design*. **40**, 237 (2012).
- [17] K. Grandfield, A. Palmquist and H. Engqvist: Three-dimensional structure of laser-modified Ti6Al4V and bone interface revealed with STEM tomography, *Ultramicroscopy*. **127**, 48 (2013).
- [18] S. Kundu, B. Mishra, D. Olson and S. Chatterjee: Interfacial reactions and strength properties of diffusion bonded joints of Ti64 alloy and 17-4PH stainless steel using nickel alloy interlayer, *Materials & Design*. **51**, 714 (2013).
- [19] S. Kundu, S. Sam and S. Chatterjee: Interfacial reactions and strength properties in dissimilar titanium alloy/Ni alloy/microduplex stainless steel diffusion bonded joints, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. **560**, 288 (2013).
- [20] X. Wang, Y. Yang, X. Luo, W. Zhang, G. Zhao and B. Huang: An investigation of Ti-43Al-9V/Ti-6Al-4V interface by diffusion bonding, *Intermetallics*. **36**, 127 (2013).
- [21] D. Verma, T. Qu and V. Tomar: Scale Dependence of the Mechanical Properties and Microstructure of Crustaceans Thin Films as Biomimetic Materials, *Jom*. **67**(4), 858 (2015). doi:DOI 10.1007/s11837-015-1337-4,
- [22] D. Verma and V. Tomar: An investigation into environment dependent nanomechanical properties of shallow water shrimp (*Pandalus platyceros*) exoskeleton, *Materials Science and Engineering: C*. **44**(0), 371 (2014). doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2014.08.033>,
- [23] D. Verma and V. Tomar: An investigation into mechanical strength of exoskeleton of hydrothermal vent shrimp (*Rimicaris exoculata*) and shallow water shrimp (*Pandalus platyceros*) at elevated temperatures, *Materials Science and Engineering: C*. **49**(0), 243 (2015). doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2015.01.003>,
- [24] D. Verma and V. Tomar: A comparison of nanoindentation creep deformation characteristics of hydrothermal vent shrimp (*Rimicaris exoculata*) and shallow water shrimp (*Pandalus platyceros*) exoskeletons, *Journal of Materials Research*. **30**(08), 1110 (2015).
- [25] K.L. Johnson and K.L. Johnson: Contact mechanics (Cambridge university press, City, 1987).

- [26] H. Somekawa and C.A. Schuh: High-strain-rate nanoindentation behavior of fine-grained magnesium alloys, *Journal of Materials Research*. **27**(09), 1295 (2012).
- [27] J.W. Elmer, T.A. Palmer and J. Wong: In situ observations of phase transitions in Ti–6Al–4V alloy welds using spatially resolved x-ray diffraction, *Journal of Applied Physics*. **93**(4), 1941 (2003). doi:doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.1537464>,
- [28] J.C. Bruhl, A.H. Varma and W.H. Johnson: Design of composite SC walls to prevent perforation from missile impact, *International Journal of Impact Engineering*. **75**(0), 75 (2015). doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2014.07.015>,
- [29] P. Follansbee and U. Kocks: A constitutive description of the deformation of copper based on the use of the mechanical threshold stress as an internal state variable, *Acta Metallurgica*. **36**(1), 81 (1988).
- [30] B. Xu and X. Chen: Determining engineering stress–strain curve directly from the load–depth curve of spherical indentation test, *Journal of Materials Research*. **25**(12), 2297 (2010).
- [31] L.H. He and M.V. Swain: Nanoindentation derived stress–strain properties of dental materials, *Dental materials*. **23**(7), 814 (2007).
- [32] G.T. Gray: High-Strain-Rate Deformation: Mechanical Behavior and Deformation Substructures Induced, *Annual Review of Materials Research*. **42**(1), 285 (2012). doi:doi:10.1146/annurev-matsci-070511-155034,